

Legend:

Figure 4. Main types of ambiguity associated with translated ncORFs in loss-of-function studies. Ambiguity types are exemplified based on the assumption that currently annotated gene models are correct. Each column corresponds to a specific location of a ncORF relative to its refORF (uORFs, uoORFs, intORFs, doORFs, and dORFs, respectively, Mudge et al., 2022). Each row corresponds to a specific scenario leading to the inactivation of one or two ORFs. The graph is a simplified illustration of the most common scenarios. It does not apply to the following situations: (1) a mutation outside both ORFs affects their transcription or translation without affecting their amino acid sequences; (2) an insertion at one location interferes with splicing at a different location, thus affecting ORFs in trans. Abbreviations: UTR, untranslated region; RNAi, RNA interference; PTGS, post-transcriptional gene silencing.